

A brief survey of the findings of toxicological exhibits of forensic samples in the Central Forensic Science Laboratory, Kolkata between 2001-2010

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Abstract : Toxicology is an important branch of forensic science. A salient feature of the present day society is apparently innocent death of a large number of victims through calculated murders or deliberately causing harms to persons. These are done by administration of high doses of sedatives, tranquillisers or antipsychotic drugs, pesticides above lethal doses, poisons mixed with alcohols, harmless drinks. Sometimes addictive poisons like methanol were utilised to make country made liquors or hooch.

2105 cases with nearly 14,000 samples (including viscera, blood, other body parts, poisoning related materials etc.) were examined by the Central Forensic Science Laboratory, Kolkata during the years 2001-2010 (up to April) received from different law enforcing investigative agencies (from Delhi to Andaman) for forensic toxicological examinations to find out, (i) the nature of crime, (ii) substances responsible for death or causing human injury and (iii) culprits of such heinous crimes.

The number of drugs, pesticides, poisons etc. are widely variable and the method of investigations are highly complex and variable and different methodologies had to be adopted to extract the pure compounds and their examinations. Routine analyses of the samples were done. But to validate the results and their authentication, sophisticated instruments like spectrophotometer, GC-FTIR, GC-MS, GC-HS, AAS, IC, HPLC and HPTLC were used.

The results of the investigation suggested that methanol, sedatives, pesticides (both organic and inorganic) have been extensively used with local variations. There is also a gradual change of use of toxicological agents with time which also varied from place to place. The investigative results are presented in this paper.

Keywords : Forensic science, toxicology, poison, drug, toxicological findings.

Introduction

World is beautiful. However, the world is polluted not only due to environmental pollution (both natural and anthropogenic) but also due to human pollution or mental aberrations like personal animosity due to greed, desire to dominate over others. This may be due to property matters, monetary superiority for family or political or social dominance and rivalries which make people to commit heinous crimes. Scientific discoveries and advancements have been directed for mischievous purposes like murder, destruction or causing harm in numerous way^{1,2}.

The use of bullets, bombs may cause enormous devastation, wounds directly to an individual or to large number of persons. But more serious concern is the clandestine use of poisons collectively known as toxic compounds, a comprehensive term used to mean the abuse of alcohols,

drugs, pesticides, poisons from plant, animal or synthetic sources, metallic or non-metallic ions, poisonous gases like CO, HCN, poisons from other sources like bacterial poisons, chemical gases (used to kill hundreds of innocent peoples) individually or collectively acting adversely on living biological (man, animal) and plant kingdom.

In fact "all things are poison and not without a poison, only the dose makes a thing poison". But generally, the compounds which are more prone to act deleteriously on the body including serious injury or even death are called toxic. This is also true for plants, animals and aquatic animals like fish. The quality or degree of being poisonous is known as toxicity and the science dealing with poisons is known as toxicology. The function of a toxicologist is to examine the compounds and perform toxicity tests to ascertain and evaluate the toxicity or risk posed to humans, animals etc. due to their uses or misuses.

However, forensic toxicology^{3,4}, a combination of analytical chemistry and fundamental toxicology, is concerned with the medico legal aspects of chemicals. A forensic toxicologist is not concerned with the drugs, doses, clinical aspects of drugs or alcohols or drug addiction leading to death or injury in a body system.

A salient feature of the present day society is apparently innocent deaths of a large number of victims by administration of high doses of poisonous alcohols, sedatives with or without alcohol, tranquilizers, pesticides, drugs etc.

However, forensic toxicologist can only examine the forensic exhibits sent to them by the crime investigating agencies arising from police or judicial inquests (legal inquiry into the circumstances and cause of suspicious death or serious injury of a person), though reports from victims (in case alive) or from the relatives of the victims (in case of a deceased) persons may also lead to police inquests.

Reviews or reports indicated sedatives diazepam and phenothiazine, CO, ethanol, nicotine, acetaminophen, salicylate, cannabinoids, pesticides, barbiturates, propoxyphene, narcotics, tricyclic-depressants, inhalants are the toxic substances used by most of the poison or suicide victims⁵⁻¹¹.

Results of five years survey of toxicological investigations and study of 601 chemical body fluid samples for the period between 2005-2009 had been published by Pillay *et al.*¹². The following drugs were identified; organophosphate pesticides (maximum), zinc phosphide, carbamate pesticides, pyrethroids, paraquat, phosphorus, bromadiolone, aluminium phosphide, sedative – hypnotics, anti-pyretic drug (paracetamol), metal ions like Pb, As, Hg and Fe, alcohol. The surveys and reports prompted us to publish our investigative analytic report for the period of 2001-2010.

Central Forensic Science Laboratory (CFSL), Kolkata is a pioneer laboratory in India for forensic investigations in which forensic toxicology is an important division to analyze forensic toxicological exhibits. 2105 cases with nearly 14,000 toxicological exhibits were examined by CFSL, Kolkata during the years 2001-2010 (April) received from different investigating agencies (from a large stretches of our country i.e. from Delhi to Andaman and

Nicobar Islands) for toxicological examinations and reports to the judiciary via investigating agencies¹³. Some of the exhibits were of trivial nature but most of the exhibits were sent after proper post mortem examinations (associated with other relevant compounds as exhibits). The viscera, blood samples, stomach wash, vomits and other relevant tissues or organs were also sent. The exhibits were sent for forensic toxicological investigations necessary to comprehend the use of the nature of substances responsible for death or causing serious injury¹⁴. The results may throw light on the nature of crimes. In general, perpetrators of crime usually leave behind some positive clues for evidences of crime according to law of individuality or principal of exchange.

The compounds were subjected to preliminary observation, clean up and separation procedures to isolate the poisons from different complex matrices before testing. Routine tests were performed to ascertain the nature of poisons. For validation and authentication of results, the experiments were performed using sophisticated instruments like FTIR, GC-HS, GC-MS, IC, HPTLC etc. The results of our investigative analysis are reported in this paper.

Materials and methods :

Materials :

Forensic exhibits from different investigative agencies formed the experimental materials. The common chemicals and solvents used were of highest purity from Merck. All the solvents used were of AR or HPLC grade (Merck).

Methods :

All the desired exhibits like viscera were subjected to preliminary clean up and Standard extraction procedures¹⁵⁻²¹ were followed depending on the nature of the samples for examination. Blood was utilized as such (like blood alcohol determination) or was subjected to standard processes of purification.

In many cases or for simple exhibits, the samples were purified and used for further analysis. Preliminary analyses of exhibits were made using standard analytical methods given in the literature^{22,33}. But the results of preliminary analysis must be validated and authenticated by checking the results by analyzing the samples using at least two sophisticated instruments of high accuracy and reproducibility as per standard forensic protocol. The lists of mea-

measurements are too many from which some of the selected measurements with results are presented with Figs. 1-9. The descriptions of the instruments used are given in Table 1.

specific complaints from the relatives or public at large.

(2) Judicial inquests.

The toxicological cases and samples as received by

Fig. 1. Chromatogram of sample (visceral extract).

Fig. 2. Chromatogram of standard endosulfan.

Fig. 3. Spectrum of endosulfan.

Discussion

It has been stated that a toxicologist has to confront an encyclopaedic mass of chemicals collectively known as poisons used or misused for poisoning and clandestine homicidal cases. However, the samples received by CFSL, Kolkata were forwarded by the crime investigating agencies and in most cases after post mortem examination of the victims. The seizures in most cases arose due to :

(1) Police inquest independently or on the basis of

CFSL are enormous. Generally, little supportive examinations were available and a toxicologist had the task of obtaining a small amount of pure materials after proper screening and purification. The clean up, screening, extraction procedures and preliminary analysis of the samples were made as per literature. However, each finding must be validated and authenticated using supportive evidence by performing at least one but preferably two confirmative analytical techniques³⁴ using sophisticated instruments.

Fig. 4. Chromatogram of sample (containing methanol) in GC-FTIR.

Fig. 5. Chromatogram of standard methanol in GC-FTIR.

Since the numbers of samples are enormous, it is not possible to give all the experimental and instrumental data in details.

It is not possible to provide all the name of poisons found in the toxicological laboratory as the names are enormous. A brief list of poisons commonly found in during the period 2001-2010 is presented in Table 2.

The task of the forensic toxicologist is to assist the judiciary with the contents or nature of poisons present in the forensic exhibits and he/she is not supposed to provide the reasons or reactions of the poisons in the biological systems unless he/she is requested to provide more detailed reports by the medical experts or judiciary. The biological details about the mode of actions of these poisons are to some extent known. But some details regarding the exhibits are presented in Tables 3-8.

Table 3 contains the year wise statistical data of the exhibits for 2001-2010 with number of exhibits analyzed and percentage of poisons found in the exhibits. Table 4 contains state wise (of India) distribution of exhibits and number of cases where poisons were detected. Table 5 contains nature and class wise statistics of poisons found in the analyzed exhibits. Table 6 contains most commonly found pesticides in the exhibits. Only 10 most commonly found pesticides were discussed. Table 7 contain the dis-

Fig. 6. Comparison of FTIR spectra of exhibit sample with standard methanol.

Fig. 7. Chromatogram of stomach extract (containing fluoride) in IC.

Fig. 8. Chromatogram of blood extract (containing fluoride) in IC.

Fig. 9. Chromatogram of standard fluoride solution in IC.

tribution of exhibits containing pesticides of Delhi and Tripura. Table 8 contain the distribution of exhibits containing poisons in the time span 2001-2006 and 2007-2010.

Table 1. Instruments used for analysis of poisons and their description

Sl. no.	Name of instrument	Model
1.	HPTLC	DESAGA CD60 densitometer, TLC applicator AS30, Video documentation system VD 40, UV chamber cabUvis
2.	Ion chromatograph	METROHM 709 IC pump, 733 IC separation centre, 732 IC detector, 753 suppressor module, 762 IC interface, 791 VA detector
3.	GC with head space sampler	Finnigan Trace GC 2000, HS 2000
4.	HPLC	JASCO, Japan PU 980 HPLC Pump, UV 975 UV detector, photo diode array detector, Shimadzu M10AVP detector and Varian Prostar 210 HPLC Pump, photo diode array detector Prostar 330 detector
5.	GCMS	Finnigan Trace GC 2000, Trace MS mass spectrograph and Perkin-Elmer Clarus 600 GC, Clarus 600T MS mass spectrograph
6.	AAS	Analytik Jena AAS Vario 6 and AAS Zeenit 60
7.	GC-FTIR	Perkin-Elmer GC Clarus 500, Interface – Spectrum GC/FTIR Interface, Detector – Spectrum GX

Though a large number of poisons were detected, but most common poisons found were ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol, phosphide, Cu salt, phenobarbital, barbital, endosulfan, DDT, malathion, chlorpyrifos, baygon, carbofuran, cypermethrin, diazepam, nitrazepam but rare and uncommon poisons were CO, F⁻, CN⁻ etc. The analysis of the exhibits showed some state wise features from which some useful conclusions may be derived.

Delhi : Ethyl alcohol was the most misused poison. Phosphide poisons were also widely used. Drug poisoning cases on the rise though pesticide poisoning showed decreasing trend but use of synthetic pyrethroid poisons were on the rise.

Tripura : Pesticides and particularly endosulfan were the main poisoning agents though use of organophosphorus poisoning was on the rise.

Table 2. Commonly found poisons in Toxicological Laboratory of Central Forensic Science Laboratory, Kolkata (classification wise)

Class of poison	Name of poison
Gaseous poison	Carbon monoxide
Volatile inorganics	Cyanide
Volatile organics	Ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol, formaldehyde, kerosene, phenol, phenyl
Non-volatile inorganics	(a) Anions Cl, SO ₄ , NO ₃ , F, Cr ₂ O ₇ , phosphide (Al or Zn)
	(b) Cations As, Pb, Cu, Hg
Non-volatile organics	(a) Basic drugs Codeine, strychnine, brucine, atropine, quinine, chloroquine, chlor-diazepoxide, benzocaine, lidocaine, promethazine, diclofenac, hydro-quinone, nimesulide, chlorpheniramine, ketamine, ibuprofen, doxepin, dothiepin
	(b) Acidic drugs Salicylic acid, barbital, phenobarbital, thiopentene, barbituric acid
	(c) Neutral drugs Diazepam, oxazepam, nitrazepam, lorazepam, alprazolam, nordazepam
Non-volatile organic pesticides	(1) Organochloro Endosulfan, DDT, aldrine, endrine
	(2) Organo phosphorus Malathion, triazophos, profenophos, chlorpyrifos, dicrotophos, dichlorvos, mevinphos, phosphamidon, parathion, methyl parathion, dimethoate, ethion, diazenone, thimate, ekalux, dithione, quinalphos, ediphenphos
	(3) Carbamate Baygon (propoxur), carbaryl, carbofuran
	(4) Synthetic pyrethroid Cypermethrin, permethrine, alphamethrine, deltamethrin
	(5) Herbicide Paraquat
Miscellaneous poisons	Abrus precatorius, oliender

Table 3. Statistical analysis of exhibits (year wise)

Sl. no.	Year	Exhibits analyzed	Exhibits containing poisonous substance	% of finding poisons in exhibits
1.	2001	2513	862	34.30
2.	2002	2782	1041	37.42
3.	2003	1173	341	29.07
4.	2004	818	287	35.09
5.	2005	673	257	38.19
6.	2006	625	212	33.92
7.	2007	789	335	42.46
8.	2008	3307	1216	36.77
9.	2009	461	189	40.99
10.	2010	950	367	38.63
	Total	14091	5107	36.24

Table 4. State wise statistics of analyzed exhibits and poisons found

Sl. no.	State/UT	Exhibits analyzed	Poisons detected
1.	Delhi	7419	2182
2.	Tripura	1509	973
3.	Andaman and Nicobar Island	1673	757
4.	Sikkim	1214	426
5.	Manipur	726	233
6.	Arunachal Pradesh	588	178
7.	Others (Jharkhand, Bhutan, Nepal, Kolkata, Government of India Organizations)	962	358

Table 5. Class wise statistics of poisons found in the analyzed exhibits

Sl. no.	Class of poison	No. of exhibits containing poison
1.	Gaseous poison	11
2.	Volatile inorganic	3
3.	Volatile organic	1494
4.	Non-volatile inorganic : (a) anions	663
	Non-volatile inorganic : (b) cations	119
5.	Non-volatile organic : (a) basic drugs	482
	Non-volatile organic : (b) acidic drugs	228
	Non-volatile organic : (c) neutral compound (i) drug	287
	Non-volatile organic : (c) neutral compound (ii) pesticides	1787
6.	Other poison (plant or animal origin)	33

Sikkim : Ethyl alcohol, Codeine, diazepam, chlorpheniramine poisoning were on the rise.

In general, ethyl alcohol (sometime mixed with methyl alcohol), drugs and pesticides poisoning were on the rise in all states. CN, CO poisoning cases were rare in all states.

However, the results pertained to the years 2001-2010, indicated a gradual shift in the use of poisons but pesti-

Table 6. Most commonly found pesticides in all the exhibits

Total exhibit	Endosulfan	Baygon	Methyl parathion	Parathion	Chlorpyriphos	Malathion	Carbofuran	Ethion	Quinalphos	Alphamethrin
1787	398	183	125	91	86	74	69	61	58	56
%	22.3	10.2	7.0	5.09	4.8	4.1	3.9	3.4	3.2	3.1

Table 7. Distribution of pesticide exhibits of (A) Delhi and (B) Tripura

	Time period pesticides	Organo-chloro pesticides	Organo-phosphorus	Carbamate pesticides	Synthetic pyrethroids	Herbicide	Total
A	2001-2006	60	33	96	22	0	211
	2007-2010	12	8	23	46	0	89
B	2001-2006	262	102	87	5	0	456
	2007-2010	85	98	57	10	3	253

Table 8. Distribution of exhibits (containing poison) in the time spans, A (2001-2006) and B (2007-2010)

Sl. no.	State	Time zone	No. of exhibits containing poison				Phosphide	Others
			Pesticides	Drugs	Volatile organics			
					EtOH	Others		
1.	Delhi	A	211	219	375	82	329	93
		B	89	241	242	29	224	48
2.	Tripura	A	456	44	48	15	-	11
		B	253	61	55	11	3	16
3.	Andaman and Nicobar Island	A	185	76	152	24		14
		B	101	89	98	9		9
4.	Sikkim	A	126	42	44	5		5
		B	80	52	58	10		4
5.	Manipur	A	66	27	28	3		2
		B	32	33	37	5		-
6.	Arunachal Pradesh	A	51	17	33	6		1
		B	25	19	19	4		3
7.	Other states	A	87	57	11	3	6	46
		B	25	20	4	84	-	15

cides and ethyl alcohol were most commonly used poisons. But the trend may be changed in recent years for which nothing could be predicted.

Lastly, it is impossible to do justice to this critical paper due to complexity and vastness of the cases. Each case deserved special emphasis to have greater insight and the author is apologetic for not providing more details in spite of a vast amount data at his disposal.

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